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ABSTRACT

The primary objective for businesses to sustain their existence is to be able to continue their operations in the long term. In order to ensure this continuity, businesses must first accurately analyze the expectations and needs of their target consumer groups and offer products or services that meet these expectations and are easily accessible. Adopting an empathetic approach during the process of introducing products and services to the market is of great importance. This is because producers are also consumers, and every individual becomes a customer of a business at some point in their life. At this stage, the main goal is to strengthen customer loyalty and increase the number of loyal consumers [7].

Businesses bear significant responsibilities in this process. Various marketing methods are utilized in the promotion of products or services, with traditional and modern marketing approaches being among the most commonly used. The primary reason for this is that consumers are influenced either positively or negatively by word-of-mouth communication during their purchasing decisions. When consumers do not have sufficient time to conduct thorough research while meeting their needs, they tend to rely on the opinions and experiences of family members, friends, or people in their close social circles. Since these individuals do not seek personal gain and are easily and quickly accessible, their opinions are perceived as more trustworthy [2].

Word-of-mouth communication, which spreads in this manner and is perceived as more impartial by consumers, plays an important role today in shaping the marketing strategies of businesses. To illustrate with a simple example, no doctor prescribes mint and lemon for the treatment of the flu; however, mint and lemon have retained their value across generations and are widely accepted in society as a natural supportive remedy. This clearly demonstrates the power of information transmitted through word-of-mouth communication.

In this study titled “The Role of Word-of-Mouth Marketing in Consumer Purchase Decisions,” the social, economic, and psychological factors influencing consumers during the purchasing process are examined [5].

Keywords: Word-of-mouth marketing, purchase decision, consumer behavior.

Introduction

Human beings have been communicating by sharing their emotions, thoughts, and experiences with one another for as long as humanity has existed. However, examining this form of communication from a marketing perspective has gained importance with the development of modern marketing concepts. In periods when the concept of marketing had not yet been systematically structured, businesses did not consider it necessary to establish direct communication with consumers and largely ignored interactions among consumers themselves. Today, however, the exchange of information and experiences among consumers occupies a central place in the purchasing process.

Consumption plays an indispensable role in individuals' daily lives. Consumers engage in consumption behavior not only to meet basic needs but also to gain experiences and achieve satisfaction. This behavior often results in the purchase of a product or service. During the purchasing decision process, consumers prefer to communicate with individuals whose knowledge and experiences they trust, rather than acting alone, in order to reduce uncertainty and perceived risk. This makes the impact of word-of-mouth marketing on purchase decisions more evident [4].

Increasing competition makes it progressively more challenging for businesses to communicate effectively with consumers. To attract the attention of a limited number of consumers and convert them into customers, businesses conduct intensive marketing activities. This intensity exposes consumers to numerous

marketing messages daily. With technological advancements, these messages appear almost everywhere consumers are present, which over time can lead to desensitization and loss of trust. At this point, consumer opinions perceived as informal and free from commercial intent gain greater credibility [1].

While businesses aim to understand consumer expectations in their marketing activities, they also seek to leverage the power of naturally occurring communication among consumers. In this context, word-of-mouth marketing refers not to direct communication between businesses and consumers, but to the sharing of positive or negative thoughts and experiences regarding products or services among consumers themselves. Consumers wish to anticipate the potential outcomes of their decisions by benefiting from the opinions of individuals who have made similar purchasing choices before. Highly satisfied consumers not only repurchase the product but can also influence the brand perception of those around them.

Therefore, it can be argued that word-of-mouth marketing plays a stronger and more effective role in consumer purchase decisions compared to traditional advertising and other marketing tools. This form of communication, perceived by consumers as more sincere, trustworthy, and impartial, has become a decisive factor in the purchasing process. Within the scope of this study, the role of word-of-mouth marketing in consumer purchase decisions is examined, focusing on

how the information and experiences obtained from individuals' social environments affect their decision-making process [6].

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

Word-of-mouth marketing is defined as the process by which individuals share their experiences and opinions about products and services with people in their social environment. Research frequently emphasizes the significant impact of this form of communication on consumers' purchase decisions. In particular, when consumers lack sufficient information about a product or service, they tend to rely on recommendations and experiences from their trusted social circle. This process reduces perceived risks and enhances the sense of confidence during the purchase decision.

Various studies indicate that the effectiveness of word-of-mouth marketing is influenced by several factors. The credibility, expertise, and social connections of the person providing the recommendation strengthen the influence of the shared information on the consumer's decision. Additionally, consumers who are satisfied with a product or service not only demonstrate a higher likelihood of repurchasing but also provide positive feedback to people around them, thereby increasing brand loyalty and customer retention. Today, electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) emerging on digital platforms has also become an effective tool in shaping online purchasing behavior.

Data from the literature suggest that word-of-mouth marketing is a more reliable and effective form of communication compared to traditional advertising and marketing methods. Consumers perceive the opinions of trusted individuals or those sharing their experiences as more sincere and convincing than advertisement messages. Therefore, word-of-mouth marketing is considered a vital strategy for businesses seeking to analyze and influence consumer behavior [5].

Methodology and Data

In this study, a questionnaire was used as the data collection method. The questionnaire consisted of a total of 33 items and was structured in three sections.

The first section included 6 items aimed at determining the demographic information of the participants. This section measured participants' gender, age, marital status, education level, occupational status, and income level.

The second section, consisting of 5 items, focused on evaluating participants' experiences in purchasing products or services through word-of-mouth marketing.

In this section, participants were asked about the category of the most recent product they purchased, the closeness of the person who influenced their purchase decision, whether they shared their experiences after purchasing the product, and which source most influenced their purchase decision. The items in this section were prepared based on the study by Aydın (2009) [3].

The third section of the questionnaire included 17 items designed to measure the effects of word-of-mouth marketing on purchase decisions. The first 3 items formed a scale assessing consumers' purchase decisions, while the following 14 items were inspired by the study of Ayaydın (2019) and aimed to measure the influence of others on consumers' purchasing processes.

The last 5 items of the questionnaire were designed to examine the effect of demographic similarity on consumer decisions. Considering that the role of demographic factors in word-of-mouth marketing has not been sufficiently addressed in the literature, these items were adapted from the scale used in Mahdum's (2020) master's thesis.

This structure allows the questionnaire to reliably and comprehensively measure both the demographic characteristics of the participants and the effects of word-of-mouth marketing on purchase decisions.

Results and Discussion

The 400 data samples collected through the questionnaires used in the study were analyzed using SPSS 26 software. The analysis process began with descriptive statistics examining the demographic characteristics of the participants and their usage of word-of-mouth communication.

Next, factor analysis was conducted to identify the dimensions of the statements included in the word-of-mouth communication and purchase decision scales. This analysis aimed to investigate potential relationships between demographic variables, the sub-dimensions of the word-of-mouth communication scale, and the purchase decision dimension.

In the final stage, statistical methods were used to analyze the relationships between the purchase decision factor and the sub-dimensions of word-of-mouth communication. This process aimed to comprehensively demonstrate both the validity of the scales and the effects of word-of-mouth communication on consumer purchase decisions.

The distribution of responses to the questions asked to determine the participants' level of engagement with word-of-mouth marketing communication is presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Participants' Usage of Word-of-Mouth Marketing Communication

Considering experience, information, advice, or opinions when purchasing goods or services	Number	Percentage
Yes	385	96.3%
No	15	3.8%
Total	400	100.0%
Product group of the last purchase made through word-of-mouth communication channel	Number	Percentage

Considering experience, information, advice, or opinions when purchasing goods or services	Number	Percentage
Cleaning Products	60	15.0%
White Goods (Home Appliances)	31	7.8%
Electronic Devices and/or Equipment	82	20.5%
Health Services	19	4.8%
Real Estate (house, car, etc.)	25	6.3%
Tourism	7	1.8%
Books/Magazines	81	20.3%
Cosmetics / Personal Care Products	86	21.5%
Other	9	2.3%
Total	400	100.0%
Relationship to the person	Number	Percentage
Family Member (mother, father, sibling)	82	20.5%
Spouse	15	3.8%
Relative	44	11.0%
Neighbor	4	1.0%
Friend	203	50.8%
Work Colleague	37	9.3%
Person met for the first time	6	1.5%
Celebrities	5	1.5%
Total	400	100.0%

Sharing positive or negative experiences with others after purchasing the product	Number	Percentage
Yes	395	98.8%
No	5	1.3%
Total	400	100.0%
The most influential source affecting the purchase decision	Number	Percentage
TV Advertisement	23	5.8%
Recommendation, information, advice	296	74.3%
Promotion	11	2.8%
Internet	59	14.8%
Other	11	2.8%
Total	400	100.0%

When participants were asked whether they purchase products by considering recommendations, information, or opinions from others, 96.3% (385 people) responded "yes," while 3.8% (15 people) answered "no." This result indicates that the vast majority of consumers make their purchasing decisions influenced by the suggestions and experiences of others.

When participants were asked about the category of the most recent product they purchased through word-of-mouth communication, the distribution was as follows: 15.0% (60) cleaning products, 7.8% (31) white goods, 20.5% (82) electronic devices, 4.8% (19) health services, 6.3% (25) real estate (house, car, etc.), 1.8% (7) tourism, 20.3% (81) books or magazines, 21.5% (86) cosmetics or personal care products, and 2.3% (9) other categories. Among those who selected "Other,"

six participants indicated clothing products, while three did not specify any category.

When asked about their closeness to the people from whom they received recommendations, information, or opinions and with whom they shared their experiences, the responses were distributed as follows: 20.05% (80) family members, 3.8% (15) spouse, 11.0% (44) relatives, 1.0% (4) neighbors, 50.8% (203) friends, 9.3% (37) colleagues, 1.5% (6) people met for the first time, and 1.5% (5) celebrities.

When participants were asked whether they shared their positive or negative experiences after purchasing a product or service with others, 98.8% (395 people) responded "yes," while 1.3% (5 people) answered "no." This finding shows that the majority of consumers share their post-purchase experiences with their social circles.

When participants were asked which source most influenced their purchase decision, the distribution of responses was as follows: 5.8% (23) television advertisements, 74.3% (296) recommendations, information, or opinions, 2.8% (11) promotions, 14.8% (59) the internet, and 2.8% (11) other sources. This result reveals that word-of-mouth communication is the most influential source on consumer purchase decisions [2].

Conclusion

This study examined the effects of word-of-mouth marketing on consumer purchase decisions, and the findings demonstrate that this form of communication plays a decisive role in consumer behavior. According to the research results, consumers place significant trust in recommendations, information, and experiences received from their close social circles when purchasing products or services. In particular, information coming from personally close sources such as family, friends, and relatives positively shapes purchase decisions and reduces perceived risk. Furthermore, consumers sharing their purchase experiences with others has an important impact on the credibility and spread of the product or service.

In this context, it is critical for businesses to emphasize word-of-mouth marketing strategies when developing their marketing plans, as this approach can both increase sales and strengthen consumer loyalty. By disseminating trustworthy and effective messages through individuals close to consumers, businesses can reach their target audience and positively influence purchasing decisions. In conclusion, word-of-mouth marketing is shown to be a more reliable, effective, and sustainable communication method compared to traditional marketing tools, and it should be utilized as a strategic instrument in modern marketing strategies.

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